

Creating Thread Supported Holes In Soap Films To Measure Their Thickness

Lior Avrahami
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ABSTRACT

We study stable thread-supported holes in soap films and use their equilibrium radius to measure film thickness. Experimental results from this method are compared with thickness estimates based on interference color bands.

THEORY

In this experiment, we prepare a soap-water mixture with density $\rho \approx 1 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{liter}} = 10^3 \frac{\text{milligram}}{\text{cm}^3}$, and from this mixture create a membrane with thickness W enclosed inside a plastic frame with dimensions $A \times B$, much like the well-known apparatus used to create soap bubbles. In this soap-water membrane, we place and suspend a loop made out of thread with linear density λ (mass per unit length). The thread stays bound to the membrane via surface tension. Next, we pop the membrane that is inside the loop, and the loop stops the rupture from propagating outside of it. Thus we are left with a hole in the water-soap membrane, which does not grow because it is halted from propagating by the thread loop. The surface tension forces on the loop from the outside keep the loop tensioned and turn it into a perfect circle; denote its radius by R .

The total force acting on the hole is gravity downward, minus the buoyancy force upward:

$$\begin{aligned} F &= mg - F_b = \lambda g \times 2\pi R - \rho V g = \\ &= 2\pi \lambda g R - \rho W \pi R^2 g = \pi g R (2\lambda - \rho W R). \end{aligned}$$

Thus there exists some critical R for which the total force on the bubble is zero, $R_c = \frac{2\lambda}{\rho W}$.

Another point is that since gravity pulls down on the water-soap in the membrane, the membrane will be thicker in the lower part than in the upper part. Thus a bubble like this one will float or sink until it comes to rest at some height, where the width of the membrane equals

$$W = \frac{2\lambda}{\rho R_c}. \quad (1)$$

In this experiment, we use a macro-scale measurement of the critical radius R_c in order to find the micro-scale membrane width W using equation (1).

Figure 1.

NOTES FOR EXPERIMENT

Two challenges were faced when trying to perform this experiment.

The first challenge was managing to consistently create these holes in the first place. Often, when bursting the film inside a loop, the loop expands violently and then abruptly stops when the thread starts to tension. This abrupt bursting and then stopping often leads to the bursting of the outer film as well, which is the opposite of what we desire. Thankfully, we found a technique that solves this problem. The proper technique involves wetting two or three fingers (depending on the size of the loop), while keeping one finger dry. Use the wet fingers to tension the loop (before popping), and then pop the film that is inside the loop using the dry finger. Using a dry finger will consistently burst the internal film, and tensioning the loop will consistently keep the bursting of the internal film from propagating to the outside of the loop.

The second challenge has to do with the fact that even after de-braiding polyester sewing thread and splitting it lengthwise into two, you still get thread that is too thick for normal-sized holes (i.e., 8 cm diameter) to float to the top of a normal-sized container (i.e., 20 cm). Our improvised solution to this was using the human hair of one of the participants instead of thread (thanks Mom). Hair proved to be **extremely** useful in this experiment. The mass density of hair is known to be $1.3 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{cm}^3}$, and the width can be easily estimated using a simple camera phone on maximum magnification, as shown in the analysis section of this document. An important note here is that we assumed that all hairs are the same. This is wrong:

Figure 2. image of hole bounded by unbraided polyester thread, not floating to the top (left); image of hole made of human hair, floating to the top (right).

Figure 3. left is braided pair of polyester strands; center is strand of hair; right is single unbraided polyester strand.

we found that different hairs can differ by a factor of 2 in their linear density. Thus, we suggest measuring the widths of each of the hairs used in the experiment, and keeping track of which is which.

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Linear Density of Hairs

Width of hairs can change by hundreds of percent from person to person. Thus this experiment must be coupled to some method of estimating the linear density (mass per unit length) of the hairs that were used. We recommend estimating the width by taking a photo; this method is easy and relatively accurate. In this experiment a standard phone camera was used (my phone camera is by no means high-end) see figure 4. The phone was placed on an improvised stand as close as possible without the phone losing the ability to focus properly.

When combined with the density of hair, which is $1.3 \frac{\text{gr}}{\text{cm}^3}$, we get $0.06 \frac{\text{milligr}}{\text{cm}} < \lambda < 0.12 \frac{\text{milligr}}{\text{cm}}$.

The main issue with the experiment we did is that we did not measure the width of the hairs that we actually used to make the loops. Thus we have a large uncertainty in λ .

Figure 4. different hairs, measured to get a distribution of hair widths.

in the middle is the polyester braided double strand for comparison.

the average widths are from left to right in $\mu\text{m} \pm 2\mu\text{m}$: 75, 76, 87, 97, 106.

Figure 5. Main snapshots, from which the main results were inferred. In the video it is apparent that the holes are mostly stationary in the up-down direction. Hole number 1 is the same in both snapshots.

Estimating Film Width From Hole Size

$$\lambda = 0.08 \frac{\text{mg}}{\text{cm}} \pm 0.03 \frac{\text{mg}}{\text{cm}}.$$

Diameter of holes 1 and 2 from figure 5 are $5.5 \text{ cm} \pm 0.05 \text{ cm}$ and $3.15 \text{ cm} \pm 0.05 \text{ cm}$.

Thus from equation (1) the widths at their locations should be:

$$\text{hole 1: } 0.58 \mu\text{m} \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$$

$$\text{hole 2: } 1.02 \mu\text{m} \pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$$

From the colors at these locations we have another estimate for the thickness:

- For hole 1, the hole resides exactly between the 3rd and 4th red stripes in both images, thus the average width is between $0.57 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.8 \mu\text{m}$. Since the average width over the hole is some average of these two numbers, let us write that it is $0.68 \mu\text{m}$.

- For hole 2, it seems to be centered around the 8th stripe (this is clearer in the video). This stripe should have width $1.7 \mu m$.

Numbers extrapolated from:
<http://markkness.net/colorpy/ColorPy.html>.

Additional Noise Sources

- Location error: the holes are not exactly stationary. They move around. This movement is smaller in the up-down direction, but is still present. Thus their location has some error. This location error can be estimated to result in width error of around $15\% \sim 20\%$.
- Perspective: perspective effects resulting from the camera direction not being exactly normal to the plane of the film could easily result in biased hole diameter measurements. Although we did try to mitigate these effects by looking only at the prin-

cipal axis of the elliptic holes, and comparing to the frame along this axis (the holes turn to ellipses because of perspective aberrations).

- Knot ears: after tying the loop, some thread must be left outside the loop to keep it from untying. This leftover thread has weight but does not have buoyancy. We estimate the error at 10% uncertainty at worst.
- As the film gets thinner, the frame drips from the bottom, thus there may exist some constant downward flow, which would exert some downward force on the holes.

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